

Barriers & Facilitators in implementing Rashtriya Bal Swasthya Karyakarm (RBSK) using Consolidated Framework of Implementation Research

Case study in the District of Rajasthan

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Abstract

Rastriya Bal Swasthya Karyakram (RBSK) was launched in 2013 to enhance the quality of life for children aged 0-18 years in India, with a focus on screening for over 40 health conditions. This study investigates organisational and administrative aspects of RBSK in Rajasthan, highlighting its positive attributes and challenges. The program, however, faces barriers including staffing shortages, financial constraints, and community resistance influenced by socio-cultural factors. Utilising the Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research (CFIR), the research examines the efficacy of staffing, outreach and community responses to the program, revealing high turnover rates and inadequate remuneration that deter qualified personnel, while bureaucratic inefficiencies impede service delivery. There is also disparity in health-seeking behaviour based on socio-economic status, with wealthier families more likely to utilize RBSK services. Poorer families resort to traditional healing methods due to perceived barriers. The findings underscore needs to improve funding, better employment conditions for staff, and enhanced community engagement to optimize RBSK's impact on child health and well-being. Ultimately, research calls for strategy enhancement of RBSK's operational framework and its integration with other health initiatives to address the systemic challenges hindering its effectiveness.

Keywords: RBSK, Rajasthan, CFIR, Implementation

1. Introduction

Children in rural Rajasthan frequently face preventable illnesses, malnutrition, and also rare diseases, all of which adversely affect their physical and cognitive development (1). India contributes 20% to global child deaths. (2) Enhancing child health services in these underserved areas is vital especially for breaking the cycle of poverty and ill health, thereby fostering sustainable social and economic progress. While India has implemented various outreach initiatives, there remains a clear need for a dedicated child health programme that actively identifies and reaches out to vulnerable children. The Rastriya Bal Swasthya Karyakram (RBSK) comes in here.

RBSK) was launched in 2013 by the Ministry of Health, Central Government. It is a health initiative designed to enhance the quality of life for children aged 0-18 years by providing comprehensive healthcare services to them. The program focuses on screening for four categories of health issues, known as the 4Ds: Defects at birth, Diseases, Deficiencies, and Developmental delays. The list of diseases is 40, and the program enables early detection, free treatment, and, when necessary, surgical interventions at tertiary care centers. (1)

RBSK has established District Early Intervention Centers (DEIC), which offer developmentally supportive care including follow-up services. Furthermore, these units link affected children with tertiary level health services in cases wherein surgical intervention is required. The Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment provides support by sponsoring equipment like hearing aids/implants and spectacles for children requiring

these. Additionally, some states have the flexibility to collaborate with private empaneled hospitals (3)

Beyond healthcare, the RBSK aims to raise awareness among rural families about the importance of child health while reducing their out-of-pocket healthcare expenses.

To facilitate the screening of children, a strong convergence has been established with other government ministries for screening children.. The newborns are screened for birth defects if any, in health facilities by the doctors and during the home visit by Accredited Social Health Activists (ASHA – peripheral health workers).

Between 2013-14 and 2022-23, in Rajasthan, approximately 52.5 million children were screened, with 2.2 million identified as having select health conditions, and 1.21 million children availed of secondary or tertiary care under the program. (4)

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Methodology

The study was conducted in a district in Northeast Rajasthan [names are kept anonymous], with the actual fieldwork limited to two medical blocks where the RBSK program is implemented. The data collection was conducted over 10 weeks in 2024 from the program implementors purposively selected for the study. In-depth interviews are carried out with the functionaries. The Research Scholar and a local social worker in the village collected data. In-depth data analysis was consensus-based and iterative, following a mixed deductive and inductive approach, using a predefined codebook that contained CFIR constructs and subconstructs organised around the five original conceptual domains.(5)

The CFIR provides an overarching typology to promote the development and verification of implementation theory, identifying what works where and why across multiple contexts. (6) The Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research (CFIR) is one of the most commonly used determinant frameworks to assess these contextual factors. (5) CFIR is a framework for assessing context in terms of existing or potential barriers and facilitators to successful implementation. The use of CFIR will depend on the type of evaluation being conducted. The CFIR is comprised of 33 constructs organised into five domains: Intervention Characteristics, Outer Setting, Inner Setting, Characteristics of Individuals, and Process that can act as barriers or facilitators to successful implementation. Intervention Characteristics is the Aspects of the intervention being implemented (e.g., complexity, relative advantage). The outer setting comprises External influences on the organisation (e.g., patient needs, external policies). Inner Setting refers to the Characteristics of the implementing organisation (e.g., culture, leadership engagement, available resources), while Characteristics of Individuals refer to the Qualities of the people involved in the implementation (e.g., knowledge, self-efficacy). The implementation process refers to how the implementation is planned, executed, and evaluated (e.g., planning, stakeholder engagement). (7,8)

Figure 1: Domain & Constructs in Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research (Damschroder et al 2022; Image adapted by Centre for Implementation)

The first step in developing a sampling strategy is to define the unit of analysis. The CFIR assesses potential barriers and facilitators within five domains. The remaining four CFIR domains rely on information elicited from individuals (and other sources such as policy documents, meeting notes, and site observations) aggregated into a collective perception. (9)

List of Individuals Interacted with and interviewed	
RBSK Field Doctors/ Staff and Clinical Doctors	
Medical Doctors in Field	4
Medical Doctors at Primary Health Centre	3
Pharmacist	2
Clinical Psychologist (DEIC) District Early Detection Centre	1
Speech Therapist (DEIC)	1
Community Health Workers	2
Professional Administration Staff	2
At School Premises	
Principal	1
Teachers	5
Students	5
Community	
Community Members	5
Patients and family Members	5

Results

Core Intervention components – Rashtriya Bal Swasthya Karyakaram: The program has set up field teams of medical and paramedic staff. RBSK's aim is to identify health problems of children. (10) The teams carry some medicines: paracetamol for fever, skin ointment for rashes, etc. In cases requiring diagnosis and more detailed intervention, children are referred to specified health facilities.

Two approaches are alternatively followed:

1. If a child is mildly indisposed, the pharmacist, on advice from the doctor, dispenses medicines
2. If a child is found to have problems that require deeper treatment in a medical facility [s]he is referred to the nearest health facility – secondary or tertiary. In this event of above, children must travel to the assigned health facilities, in most cases at their own cost. (11)

RBSK – Observation from the field: Meetings were held with the program staff, the health facility staffs, schools, 10 families of children who have received treatment under RSBK, and communities in two villages.

The Location

Northeast Rajasthan is socially backward: as in 2021, women with 10 years of education was 37%, and a quarter of the girls under 18 years were married. About 41% children under 5-years were stunted. [About 95% babies are institutionally delivered [10] and examined/treated at birth for any disease].

Each field team of an RBSK medical block consists of two field medical teams consisting of four personnel: two physicians, one pharmacist and one social worker/ paramedic. The teams reach out to schools and pre-school [1-2 times a year], but not elsewhere for want of resources. The teams are provided with transport for field visit.

In the RSBK's district office [DEIC] had a staff of 11 personnel consisting of doctors, dentists, and social workers/ counsellors. However, at the time of survey there were only four personnel in place: we were told that full staff has never been achieved. There is about 70% overall staff shortage at any time, including in field staff due to perpetual delays in appointments. Also problematic are unending financial shortages and unwarranted bureaucratic procedures. In fact, Indian authorities announce increased numbers of health programs from time to time without raising the health budget. Each programme is thus thinly stretched, compromising the gravitas of the program.

The RBSK staff, are employed on contract; some have served for a decade without experiencing a change in their employment status. Multiple representations have been made to the government for better remuneration and employment conditions, but these have not yielded any results. It is not surprising that the doctors employed under RBSK are trained in Traditional Indian medicine; the program is unable to attract allopathy-trained staff due to low salaries and employment conditions. There is high staff turnover: many skilled employees leave for opportunities elsewhere, impacting efficiency. Between April and December 2024, approximately 54% of the targeted children in a district were screened – with just 3 months in the financial year remaining, screening 100% seems impossible.

Calculating allocations versus impact of RBSK at local levels is difficult since patient-identification is done by the mobile medical teams, while the treatment is done at government facilities. There was, nevertheless, a general complaint about delay in release of funds at by all: the programme staff and at the health facilities.

At another level, it is seen that while the doctors are traditional Indian medicine-trained, the medicines dispensed by the field staff are from an allopathic stream - An anomaly? Furthermore, an issue pointed out was the deployment of RSBK programme staff on non-programme duties like those for elections or census. This also reduces the efficiency and motivation of the personnel.

The single largest health problem, as seen from field data maintained at both block and district levels, is anaemia [995 out of 3,458 total referred cases], followed by vision impairment [570 out of the referred cases] in the district [Table 2].

Anaemia could stem from the health condition of the mother during pregnancy, childbirth, or breastfeeding; the overall diet at home, or quality of drinking water in homes. While taking supplements may provide temporary relief, anaemia could strike back once the doses are depleted.

Spectacles for children's weak eyesight are to be provided by the government, but due to resource-limitations and bureaucracy there are huge delays.

Health facilities

In the health facilities as well, there are vacant positions of both physicians and auxiliary staff.

In one middle-level health facility visited, the number of doctors' positions sanctioned was seven but there were only three in place including a dentist. This was a complaint elsewhere as well. The selecting authorities and appointing authorities being different, compounds the problem.

Box 1: Doctors at the DEIC, in the field, and at PHCs expressed their appreciation for the RBSK program. One remarked, "It has given us the opportunity to directly interact with children and understand their clinical issues—many of which would have otherwise gone unnoticed."

A field doctor noted, "The process of screening followed by treatment has led to noticeable improvements in children's health. However, sustained efforts are still needed to effectively address malnutrition and anemia."

Doctors at the district and block health facilities reported that RBSK is just one of these 30 health schemes run by the government [state and centre]. Children referred to the facilities join the general queue of all patients in the health facilities...no special treatment. The RBSK staff's efforts for linking-up with private hospitals has so far not been successful, at least in this area.

Most patients also prefer going to private health providers despite them being expensive and at times not too scientific. They prefer these so-called health-dispensers for sociocultural reasons and because of familiarity with them.

Schools

Government schools have their own state-government-promoted health programs and links with the local health facilities. They have little or no idea about functioning of RBSK. The RBSK team does not interact with the school staff nor are the school data on children's health shared with them: state-government/central-government jurisdiction gap.

Box 2: Student: A 6th-grader student, had experienced skin rashes. She shared, "When the RBSK team visited our school, the doctors gave me an ointment and advised me to go to the Primary Health Centre (PHC) if the rashes didn't improve. Later, they followed up with a phone call and referred me to a skin specialist at the PHC. I was prescribed oral medication and another ointment. Since it was difficult for me to visit the PHC with my parents, I bought the ointment from the market. The treatment has been helping me."

In the preschools there is greater interaction between the RBSK staff and the preschool teachers. Many teachers here [it is always females] though underpaid use their own resources like mobile phones to reach out to RBSK personnel about children's health issues. However, the children at this level are small and in each case a health issue must be discussed with parents, who might not be always willing. Next, not being trained in paramedics, the preschool teachers are at loss on many health issues or in emergencies.

Box 3: Pre-school: A middle-aged and experienced health worker, serves at an Anganwadi center that caters to preschool children. She looks after around 18 children. "One of the children is a frail five-year-old girl, prone to frequent colds and coughing. I give her over-the-counter medicines at the advice of the RBSK team. I also ensure this child avoids any physically demanding activities".

In the next 6 to 8 months, the girl will turn six and transition to a regular primary school. "I worry whether she will receive the same level of care there? I am unsure whether primary schools even conduct thorough health screenings during admissions. Do the RBSK share the health records of children when they are transferred to their new schools?"

Interaction with Village Communities

The village heads generally knew about the programme because in their official positions. They also interacted with the RBSK functionaries. However, all they knew was that this is yet another government children health program, and that their teams occasionally visit schools/ preschools for check-ups.

Village-level observations about RBSK

- The relatively more affluent families [mostly from dominant castes], who had received some education and were exposed to urban areas, appreciated the program, and praised the medical teams for their efforts.
- Of specific praise was the effort made by the medical teams and preschool teachers in helping children in need of medical intervention to health centres beyond the call of duty.
- Many poorer families who were less exposed to the external world, preferred not to have treatment of minor illnesses; they believed that these illnesses would cure by themselves. These families also expressed hesitation in interacting with the modern health system as it would entail travel many miles to a town and go through administrative processes before seeing a health provider.
- Some feared that the visiting Mobile Health Teams were commission agents; they work for cash returns in lieu of sending patients for treatment.
- Many families, after the first consultation, pursue alternative indigenous treatment from local healers, who had no formal degrees. Reason: comfort of the environment in the home region.

Girl children's illnesses, which could include minor and serious ones, were generally ignored compared to those of boys by almost all.

When the village leaders were shown the number of children treated after the RBSK had identified them, they stood their ground: either many households did not come forward to report the health problems of their children or the records were not accurate. The former seems to hold some ground since the M&E system is such that photographs of each of the visits are sent through WhatsApp to the district headquarters.

Box 4: Patient Family: Father of a 13-year-old boy who underwent treatment and surgery for a hole in his heart, shared: "It was the RBSK team that first detected our son's heart condition. Initially, we were hesitant about going ahead with the treatment, but with their encouragement and support, we decided to proceed with the surgery at an affordable cost. Although our son still feels weak and cannot engage in activities for long periods, we are grateful that he is with us."

Interaction with Families of the Children Treated Under the Aegis of RBSK

The research team interacted with at least 10 families whose children were identified to be requiring health interventions. In one case a child aged about 14 years had a ventricular septal defect. He received treatment through RBSK intervention in a district hospital. The boy is in better health now, though he is still extremely weak and gets tired quickly. His parents feel that he might not have survived if the RBSK team did not help. Two children, each aged about 5-6 years in two families had suffered from acute anaemia. One case was referred to the district hospital for blood transfusion and seems to have recovered. The other case was not so acute, and regular doses of folic acid and vitamins have helped. Again, the parents praised the RBSK team for help. A girl aged about 10 years in another family received skin ointment from the RBSK mobile medical team to treat persistent itching that she suffered from. She seemed to be feeling better at the time of our interaction. All the three families were not poor, and they belonged to the dominant caste in the region.

The converse: A general discussion with the poorer village community brought out some apprehensions:

- People were apprehensive to travel for treatment because of the expenses involved on travel and stay in a city, though they knew that there would be no expense on treatment.
- In some cases when medicines or diagnostic tests are not available in the hospital stock, patients are asked to do to the market, for which they must expend monies.
- A few feared that in the name of vitamins and folic acid tablets, they are given tablets to control fertility, especially when prescribed for girls aged 13+ years.

- There is doubt that medicines given by mobile medical team and in health centres are of the same potency when compared to branded medicines available at medical shops, making recovery is slow.

Challenges identified using CFIR Framework

The CFIR comprises five major domains (the intervention, inner and outer setting, the individuals involved, and the process by which implementation is accomplished). These domains interact in rich and complex ways to influence implementation effectiveness. More than 20 years ago, Pettigrew and Whipp emphasized the essential interactive dimensions of content of intervention, context (inner and outer settings), and process of implementation. The CFIR Framework analyses the implementation process in granular detail by identifying both the institutional settings and personnel and working of the system, permits to determine key aspects augmenting or retard achieving goals. (12) It has five key elements. Each of these are discussed with the RBSK data presented above.

Interventions Characteristics

The main stakeholders of the intervention in RBSK are at least three levels: intervention with schools and preschools, intervention with the families of children identified as requiring some medical or health inputs, and intervention with health providers. A list of agencies in the process in the sequence of intervention are:

1. Mobile Medical Team
2. School and preschool staff
3. Children's parents
4. Transport system
5. Health providers at different levels
6. RBSK district office [DEIC] (7)

If the mobile medical teams are weak, the chain would be adversely affected from the very beginning. Here, while the mobile team members are highly motivated, the number of staff members are much fewer that required almost everywhere. A simple count suggests that if the full program's efficiency is expected to be Z , then if mobile team members are about half the strength, then the efficiency will be $< Z$, if not half. Owing to low salaries, high turnover and staff assigned to external duties like in elections, the efficiency ' Z ' is further affected.

This inference is supported by data seen from Table 1, where it is seen that the total children screened was over 130 thousand, while those referred for treatment were only about 3,400, i.e., $< 3\%$. This is against figures of stunted or underweight children, which exceeded 40,000 in the area as per government data. Surely, there should be greater convergence between these two figures.

[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]	[7]	[8]
RBSK Block	Target Boys	Target girls	Total	Screened Boys	Screened girls	Total	% Screened
Block C	9459	10709	20168	6485	8052	14537	72.08
Block D	29127	30244	59371	13533	172286	30819	51.91
Block E	10014	9731	19745	5580	5802	11382	57.64
Block F	22540	22112	44652	11290	14301	25591	57.31
Block A & B	21525	24681	46205	10030	13676	23706	51.31
Block G	23270	26880	50150	10570	13936	24506	48.87
Total	115935	124357	240292	57488	73053	130541	54.33

Table 1: RBSK's Screening Report in a Large District in Eastern Rajasthan, April-December 2024

Table 1 also shows that there are differences in the proportion of those screened across the medical blocks, ranging from about 49% to about 72%. This is yet another symptom of insufficiency in staff, staff deployment in other activities, and financial constraints.

Outer Setting

Agencies: School, Preschool

While the school/ preschool authorities were cooperative, the active association of the school staff was not high. A central government program seems to have little or no truck with the local institutions. This is evident also from the fact that the numbers of children referred from the preschools, which come under the central government, are significantly larger than those referred from schools which come under the state government [Table 2]. Note: The number of children in preschools are much fewer compared to those in schools.

Inner Settings

Agencies: Health facilities, DEIC

- Once cases are referred to a health facility, they join the same queue for meeting a doctor as other patients. This is time-consuming, adding to inefficiency.
- The DEIC faces staff shortage, high turnover, etc., affect its effectiveness.
- Cost is also a factor here. One is the travel to the health facilities. Rajasthan's villages are well connected by roads and buses (8). However, there is a cost attached to travelling. In some cases when medicines are not available or pathological/radiological tests are done outside in the market, the costs go further up. Not all users are ready to spend the monies and efficiency is adversely affected.

Process of Implementation

Agencies: All listed in Intervention Characteristics above

Table 2 shows that against a target of 120 screenings per day, the numbers fall short in all the teams, with one team showing zero screenings: this team had no staff in this period. Next, there is a gap to an extent of 22% between those referred to those treated: it is ranging from about 40% in one team to 100% in other teams. At the same time, the performance of three teams exceeds 90%. These gaps are explained by implementation factors: problems in getting access to the health facilities, transport and travel, and belief systems [discussed earlier]. At this stage, however, it is not possible to quantitatively isolate the impact of each of them.

[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]	[7]	[8]
RBSK Block	Per day, per day screening	Number of referred cases	Numbers treated	Numbers remaining	% Treated	Numbers identified from school	Numbers identified from Anganwadis
Block D, Team 2	99.05	268	108	160	40%	94	180
Block D, Team 1	86.53	464	427	37	92%	68	118
Block C, Team 1	84.39	655	533	122	81%	91	160
Block G, Team 2	78.79	313	306	7	98%	75	152
Block E, Team 2	78.7	436	307	129	70%	65	124
Sewar Team 2	73.63	343	149	194	43%	73	128
Block A, Team 2	71.89	192	192	0	100%	77	153
Block A, Team 1	69.22	196	196	0	100%	91	144
Block F, Teams 1 and 2	67.75	424	308	116	73%	40	197
Block G, Team 1	67.08	167	158	9	95%	104	156
Block C Team 2	0	0	0	0	-	0	0
Total	77.70	3458	2684	774	78%	781	1512

Table 2: Team-wise Progress, April-December 2024, District D

Characteristics of Individuals

Not in all cases do parents cooperate. The relatively more exposed, educated and affluent parents have come forward to take advantage of the scheme; however, the poorer, less education and less exposed are apprehensive. This socioeconomic class differentiation is a certain factor affecting efficiency.

Conclusion

Good health cannot be achieved by medical interventions alone. Health is an integral part of development and unless other components of development like education, incomes and lifestyles improve, health interventions like RBSK alone will have limited impact.

It is reported that over time, early interventions have helped fewer children being referred for advanced treatment; instead, their ailments are treated at an early stage. It has, however, not reached anywhere near the knowledge-level that say other problems like ICDS have reached. Furthermore, there are several problems with the programme, and several endemic issues regarding community health and interventions.

As for the program, the major constraints are in the budgets. Unless there are more funds provided, the quantity and quality of services will remain constrained. In the same context, it needs statement that multiplicity of programmes and schemes with degrees of overlap create duplication and reduce the effectiveness of programmes like the RBSK, in addition to adding to wastages.

On personnel, the government's approach of appointing staff on contract and low salaries is a major limitation to the RBSK. There is a perpetual shortage of staff and there is high turnover of staff in addition to disgruntlement among the personnel.

The success of RBSK also program hinges on the active participation and collaboration of different stakeholders from health and educational department to panchayati raj institutions. Their roles and contributions collectively determine the reach, quality, and sustainability of the program, ultimately impacting the health and well-being of children.

So, should RBSK stay or merged with programs? Health planners need to give a serious thought to this.

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